

Probe Set ID	Gene Symbol	Chromosome Number	pvalue ([wt] Vs [ko])	FCAbsolute ([wt] Vs [ko])	Authors' Comments
1451148_at	Pink1	chr4	6,97E-05	48,452423	KO
1441937_s_at	Pink1	chr4	9,74E-05	45,783978	KO
1424524_at	Dram1 - 1200002N14Rik	chr10	1,37E-04	1,7332038	Dram1 DNA-damage regulated autophagy modulator 1; implicated in PARK2 variants of Parkinson's disease (Tatura-R 2016 Parkinsonism Relat Disord)
1452730_at	1110033J19Rik	chr6	2,23E-04	2,0384903	Rps4l ribosomal protein S4-like
1422616_s_at	Wdr54	chr6	5,54E-04	1,7951214	
1429118_a_at	Gin1 - 4930429M06Rik	chr1	6,74E-04	1,78669	Gin1 gypsy retrotransposon integrase 1
1436359_at	Ret	chr6	9,93E-04	1,7081106	PINK1/Parkin interactions with RET: Klein-P 2014 EMBO J for PINK1, Meka-DP 2015 J Clin Invest for Parkin
1436462_at			0,001027774	1,9132199	
1428991_at	Hrasls	chr16	0,001528755	2,8665628	
1448239_at	Hmox1	chr8	0,001866731	1,7795864	cleaves the heme ring and liberates iron; innate immunity factor; crucial for mitochondrial quality control; implicated in Parkinson's disease (Schipper-HM 2015 Int J Mol Sci; Wegliel-B 2015 Free Radic Biol Med; Hull-TD 2016)
1454714_x_at	Phgdh - LOC546010	chr7	0,002202771	124,833885	
1427730_a_at	Zfp148	chr16	0,003365849	1,630802	
1424257_at	Cdk7	chr13	0,004854731	2,1732583	
1432443_at	1700021P22Rik	chr7	0,004899022	1,543802	Golgi-associated Rab2B interactor-like 5
1418172_at	Hebp1	chr6	0,004931319	1,8345174	heme binding protein 1, includes a natural chemoattractant peptide of 21 amino acids at the N-terminus, which is a natural ligand for formyl peptide receptor-like receptor 3 (FPRL3) and promotes calcium mobilization and chemotaxis (Devosse-T 2011)
1456490_at	Cdk2ap2	chr19	0,00539204	1,8029057	
1456565_s_at	Map3k12	chr15	0,005866624	1,8616774	
1451680_at	Srxn1	chr2	0,006438374	1,5373628	oxidative stress resistance
1426766_at	6330403K07Rik	chr11	0,00683536	1,8228908	UGS148, involved in intracellular sorting, trafficking, exocytosis and membrane insertion
1417602_at	Per2	chr1	0,006929158	1,5086643	
1434735_at	Hlf	chr11	0,008153346	1,5317298	upstream of HIF1alpha
1429241_at	Npal3	chr4	0,008624177	2,5109963	
1424938_at	Steap1	chr5	0,009155522	1,9902649	Metalloreductase that has the ability to reduce both Fe(3+) to Fe(2+) and Cu(2+) to Cu(1+). Uses NAD(+) as acceptor
1432372_a_at	Spr	chr6	0,009455642	1,6994692	Dopa-responsive dystonia and Parkinsonism
1432217_a_at	1700019F09Rik	chr11	0,009735948	2,368865	WDRPUH, with WD40 repeat, cilia- and flagella-associated protein 52
1431708_a_at	Tia1	chr6	0,010277364	4,357368	starvation regulator at stress granules
1430837_a_at	Mbd1	chr18	0,010326727	3,3089137	Regulator Of Fibroblast Growth Factor 2 (FGF-2) Transcription
1437753_at			0,010944241	1,5809302	
1436045_at	Tsga10	chr1	0,010945085	1,9227682	prevents nuclear localization of HIF1alpha
1456256_at	Eif5	chr12	0,011162037	1,6740198	
1456041_at	Snx16	chr3	0,013978108	1,5146377	promotes degradation of EGFR after stimulation, intracellular transport of vesicular stomatitis virus nucleocapsids (Le Blanc-I 2005 Nat Cell Biol)
1421009_at	Rsad2	chr12	0,014488435	1,7024405	Interferon-inducible iron-sulfur (4FE-4S) cluster-binding antiviral protein (Chen-WQ 2015 Dev Comp Immunol)
1442165_at	Armc9	chr1	0,015487114	1,840675	
1449862_a_at	Pi4k2b	chr5	0,016058756	1,8411335	
1422256_at	Sstr2	chr11	0,017115435	1,7433645	mediates negative regulation of insulin receptor signaling
1452992_at	Cdc26	chr4	0,017132841	1,52979	Component of APC/C complex, a cell cycle-regulated E3 ubiquitin ligase
1455279_at	Gm1060	chr5	0,018250158	2,1300688	
1432189_a_at	Sox5	chr6	0,01899819	1,6616669	
1460227_at	Timp1	chrX	0,019330187	1,5041677	inducible by cytokines and toll-like receptors (Li-L 2014 Mol Cell Biochem; Swanberg-M 2006 Neurobiol Dis)
1450432_s_at	Mus81	chr19	0,019486142	1,5867147	Up-regulated in cells treated with agents that damage DNA or block replication
1434894_at	3110050K21Rik	chr14	0,019493764	1,6834528	Zc3h13 zinc finger CCCH type containing 13
1436519_a_at	1110057K04Rik	chr12	0,019745862	1,5311022	Ldah lipid droplet associated hydrolase
1423667_at	Mat2a	chr6	0,020037618	1,6003249	hypoxia induces DNA demethylation through Mat2a upregulation
1456471_x_at	LOC224870 - Phgdh	chr3	0,021097671	22,651728	
1427524_a_at	4930548G07Rik	chr14	0,021225194	1,5558258	Mphosph8 M-phase phosphoprotein 8
1451621_at	5830417C01Rik	chr1	0,021344382	1,6901493	Desi2 desumoylating isopeptidase 2
1423500_a_at	Sox5	chr6	0,022289125	1,5124487	
1455064_at	Rab36	chr10	0,02343256	1,7044375	
1457264_at	Phf2011	chr15	0,023548324	1,7924849	influences DNA cytosine methylation via DNMT1 (Estève-PO 2014 J Biol Chem)
1421752_a_at	Serpib5	chr1	0,023890194	1,5496114	tumor suppressor, interactor of interferon regulatory factor 6
1422725_at	Mak	chr13	0,024152678	2,2695055	

1424253_at	1810073G14Rik	chr11	0,024282003	1,6238674	
1421441_at	Angpt1	chr15	0,024920227	1,5130731	
1435688_at			0,02493906	2,226304	
1460006_at	Atbf1	chr8	0,02682056	1,7013267	
1417988_at	Resp18	chr1	0,0270382	2,6684775	RESP18 is involved in the cytotoxicity of dopaminergic neurotoxins in MN9D cells, overexpression aggravated cell death induced by MPP+ and 6OH-DA
1435036_at	A530050D06Rik	chr12	0,027661307	1,7793468	Aspg asparaginase homolog
1425191_at	9430098E02Rik	chr8	0,029728629	1,5816218	Ocel1 occludin/ELL domain containing 1, NRF1 target like PINK1
1419749_at	Dnmt2	chr2	0,029773517	1,5979004	cytosine methylation of RNA and DNA; role in stress granules represents a defense mechanism against viral infection (Schaefer-M 2010 Genes Dev)
1427133_s_at	LOC545422	chr2	0,030742085	1,5075078	
1434510_at	Papss2	chr19	0,030916411	1,6075696	sulfation activation pathway; expression regulated by lipopolysaccharide treatment; neighbor gene of PTEN (Kim-MS 2004 Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab; Marbiah-MM 2014 EMBO J; Liu-Z 2016 Free Radic Biol Med)
1436058_at	Rsad2	chr12	0,03116718	1,7421006	Interferon-inducible iron-sulfur (4FE-4S) cluster-binding antiviral protein (Seo-JY 2011 Cell Host Microbe; Chen-WQ 2015 Dev Comp Immunol)
1421141_a_at	Foxp1	chr6	0,031862367	1,7421789	modulated by alpha-synuclein, responsible for DAergic midbrain neurons
1431630_a_at	Klf3	chr5	0,032135975	1,8721375	Binds to the CACCC box of erythroid cell-expressed genes, regulated by Interleukin-17, regulates inflammatory Galectin-3 (Ahmed-M 2013 Cytokine; Knights-AJ 2016 J Biol Chem)
1455260_at	A830039H10Rik	chr5	0,032324962	1,5346051	
1429380_at	Rgs12	chr5	0,03331049	1,7056541	Ras/Raf/Mek-scaffold in nerve-growth-factor-mediated differentiation
1434929_at	BC035044	chr6	0,033569746	1,6217262	
1453470_a_at	Gna13	chr11	0,033591755	1,5725456	interacts with RhoGEF
1426631_at	C330017115Rik	chr5	0,03389128	1,5001372	Pus7 pseudouridylylase synthase 7 homolog
1441306_at	6820408C15Rik	chr2	0,03397604	2,9458206	
1429588_at	2810474O19Rik	chr6	0,034188952	1,9378095	
1452595_at	Adams4	chr1	0,03418908	1,8432097	induced by interleukin-1, repressed by hyaluronan (Bondeson-J 2007 J Rheumatol; Yaikasli-KO 2009 Mol Cell Biochem; Yatabe-T 2009 Ann Rheum Dis)
1435642_at	9630019K15Rik	chr17	0,034402315	2,4065404	Prr18, proline rich 18
1449390_at	Gpatc4	chr3	0,035351932	1,5143058	
1423997_at	Csde1	chr3	0,03547374	1,7396368	synonymous to UNR; internal initiation of translation of virus RNA; regulation of c-Fos RNA (Grosset-C 2000 Cell; Boussadia-O 2003 J Virol)
1426114_at	Hnrpab	chr11	0,03590401	1,5990748	binds single-stranded RNA
1439582_at	Macf1	chr4	0,03621851	1,9254653	Wnt signaling pathway of wound healing
1434315_at	Npal3	chr4	0,036787618	1,8032653	
1452139_at	Slc35c1	chr2	0,037324883	1,6265639	GDP-fucose import from the cytoplasm into the Golgi lumen
1422919_at	Hrasls	chr16	0,03812369	1,9519243	
1435529_at	Ifit3	chr19	0,038313616	1,5106372	enhances MAVS-mediated host antiviral responses, as adaptor leading to activation of TNFR-associated factor family member-associated NF-kB activator-binding kinase 1 (TBK1) (Liu-XY 2011 J Immunol)
1419069_at	Rabgef1	chr5	0,03857006	1,606571	
1427942_at	Pamci	chr10	0,03936968	1,8311158	endosomal RASSF9
1422253_at	Col10a1	chr10	0,039610066	2,9920065	
1421321_a_at	Net1	chr13	0,040916238	1,6481261	Rho-GEF Proto-Oncogene P65, induced by TGFB1, in JNK pathway
1434868_at	4933431E20Rik	chr3	0,041321814	1,808017	
1429566_a_at	Hipk2	chr6	0,041372046	1,5986654	response to hypoxia by acting as a transcriptional co-suppressor of HIF1A, involved in p53/TP53-mediated cellular apoptosis
1448566_at	Slc40a1	chr1	0,041440252	1,9830165	iron-regulated transporter; regulated by toll-like receptors and lipopolysaccharides; dysregulated in Parkinson's disease (Layoun-A 2012 Am J Pathol; Rhodes-SL 2014 Neurobiol Dis)
1417481_at	Ramp1	chr1	0,0420383	1,9016539	
1425349_a_at	Myef2	chr2	0,042601384	2,0290363	
1428751_at	Pacrg	chr17	0,044120647	1,5269926	
1424966_at	Tmem40	chr6	0,044930708	1,5544113	
1448417_at	Ninj1	chr13	0,045032132	1,5059755	upregulated after nerve injury
1419420_at	St6galnac5	chr3	0,0450764	1,626536	
1422033_a_at	Cntf	chr19	0,045293726	1,5433439	Liu-J 2010 Proteomics, von Bohlen und Halbach-O 2009 Adv Exp Med Biol
1429217_at	Zfp655	chr5	0,045893386	1,7568653	
1428599_at	2410012C07Rik	chr7	0,04663539	1,507578	
1435069_at	BC064078	chr6	0,046687637	1,6245518	
1455147_at			0,04702163	1,697666	
1424098_at	Elovl7	chr13	0,04778445	1,5016968	Elongation Of Very Long Chain Fatty Acids

1417618_at	Itih2	chr2	0,048334748	2,5506465	
1445404_at	Kif27	chr13	0,04843511	1,5450956	
1440147_at	Lgi2	chr5	0,0489945	2,0282414	phenotype epilepsy
1429059_s_at	1110004B13Rik	chr11	0,049165368	1,7148007	Tmem107 transmembrane protein 107
1453734_at	Atrx	chrX	0,049633674	1,5523869	PML nuclear body component involved in antiviral defense (Scherer-M 2016 J Virol)
1427944_at	C1qdc1	chr6	0,049639553	1,6935508	

Color coding:

Pink1-KO

trophic factors

already implicated in neurodegenerative processes

DNA/RNA quality control

hypoxia/antioxidant factors

autophago-lysosomal modulator

vesicle trafficking

anti-microbial state factors